

A Spatial Analysis of Fast-Food Outlet Density Around London Schools: Implications for Policy and Planning

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Summary

The rising prevalence of childhood obesity has been linked to changes in the neighbourhood food environment, prompting the inclusion of takeaway management zones in the revised 2024 National Planning Policy Framework. This study examines fast-food outlet density around London schools to guide policymakers on distance thresholds for their management zones. Using R5R accessibility analysis, we found the highest concentrations of fast-food outlets within a 15-minute walk of schools. However, distributions vary across boroughs, reflecting one of four spatial patterns. Local authorities should implement management zones within 15-minutes of schools, at minimum, to cover areas with highest exposure to fast-food outlets.

KEYWORDS: Spatial Inequalities, Public Health, Obesogenic Environments, Accessibility Analysis, Schools & Fast-food Outlets

1. Introduction

In London, 20% of four year old children and more than 38% of 10 year old children were living with obesity in 2022/2023 (House of Commons Library, 2023). Childhood obesity is more prevalent in London than in the rest of England; for instance, in 2022/2023, 24.8% of Year 6 children in London were living with obesity, compared to 22.7% in England (Office for Health Improvement & Disparities, 2022).

The rising prevalence of obesity has been linked to changes in the neighbourhood food environment (Da Costa Peres et al., 2019; Jiang et al., 2022). Over recent decades, high-income countries have experienced a proliferation of fast-food outlets selling cheap, energy-dense foods that are heavily promoted and incentivised (Swinburn et al., 2011). London has a particularly high density of fast-food outlets, with rates of 97 – 118 outlets per 100,000 population (Local Government Association, 2021). Of particular concern is the number of new fast-food outlets opening around important places for children and young people, such as schools. According to research by Smith et al. (2013), between 2001 and 2005, 17 new fast-food outlets opened within 400 metres of secondary schools in East London, making processed foods, high in sugar, fat, and salt more easily accessible to children.

In response, policymakers have called for measures to restrict children's access to unhealthy food environments. In 2014, Public Health England (PHE) recommended introducing takeaway management zones to limit the number of fast-food outlets near schools (Public Health England, 2014). However, implementation had remained at the discretion of local authorities, leading to inconsistent specification of regulations across London boroughs and relatively low uptake (Rahilly et al., 2024).

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This changed in December 2024, when the National Planning Policy Framework was updated to include takeaway management zones (Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2024). Local authorities are now required to restrict new fast-food outlets from opening within walking distance of schools. However, no prior research has determined the walking distance that typically captures a high density of fast-food outlets around schools in London, which could support the adoption and implementation of correctly specified zones that include areas of high exposure.

This study aims to address this knowledge gap by analysing the spatial distribution of fast-food outlets in relation to schools in London. These findings can be used to help local authorities identify areas of greatest need and prioritise the implementation of management zones in areas already saturated with fast-food outlets.

2. Methods

To examine the spatial distribution of fast-food outlets in relation to schools, an accessibility analysis was conducted using Rapid Realistic Routing (R5) in R (R5R). This approach generated accessibility surfaces around schools, allowing for the assessment of fast-food outlet intensity (i.e., density) within these areas.

2.1 School data

UK Government data on school locations was used from the 31st December 2021. This date was chosen to align with the timeframe of the fast-food outlet data used in the study. The data were filtered to include only operational schools in London, excluding universities and nursery schools.

2.2 Fast-food outlet data

Fast-food outlet data were obtained from Ordnance Survey Points of Interest data for December 2021 and included outlets that fell into the categories of "Fish and Chip Shops," "Fast Food and Takeaway Outlets," and "Fast Food Delivery Services". Non-fast-food points removed from the dataset through manual cleaning.

2.3 R5 Analysis

Using OpenStreetMap data, a transport network was set up to calculate walking travel-time matrices between schools (origins) and hexagonal grid centroids (destinations) across London boroughs. Walking travel times were computed (maximum 30 minutes) and mapped to the spatial grid, which was then converted to a raster surface (Figure 1).

2.4 Rhohat Analysis

Fast-food outlet locations were converted into planar point patterns (ppp objects) within borough-specific spatial windows, using the British National Grid (EPSG: 27700). To analyse the relationship between fast-food outlet density and proximity to schools, we used the rhohat function in R, which provides a nonparametric estimate of point process intensity as a function of a spatial covariate. Specifically, the rhohat statistic was used to estimate how the intensity (i.e., density) of fast-food outlets varies with walking travel times to schools. Rhohat plots (Figure 2) were then used to compare outlet densities across different walking time bands and London Boroughs.

2.5 Visualisation of Results

From the Rhohat plots, density curves were extracted and overlaid for all 32 London boroughs (Figure 3). The graph was then visually assessed to identify patterns, with boroughs categorised into distinct groups based on variations in the shape of the density curves and the relative density of fast-food outlets near schools.

3. Results

In London, there were 9,275 fast-food outlets and 2,950 schools. The R5 analysis revealed a distinct spatial pattern in the distribution of fast-food outlets relative to schools. Across London, the greatest density of fast-food outlets was observed within a 15-minute walk of schools, with densities declining as walking time increased (Figure 3). However, the magnitude and shape of these density curves varied across boroughs and could be categorised into four distinct spatial patterns:

3.1 Strong Peak with Gradual Decline

Boroughs such as Barking and Dagenham, Croydon, Harrow, and Lewisham demonstrated a pronounced peak in outlet density in close proximity to schools (within a 5–10 minute walk), followed by a gradual decline in density that levelled off beyond 15 minutes (Figure 4).

3.2 Strong Peak with Noticeable Secondary Peaks

In contrast, boroughs including Brent, Greenwich, Hammersmith & Fulham, and Westminster exhibited an initial density peak that persisted over a broader range (up to 10 minutes of walking time), followed by a more gradual decrease. Notably, many of these boroughs also showed secondary peaks at greater distances, indicating additional clusters of fast-food outlets beyond the immediate vicinity of schools (Figure 5).

3.3 Sustained High Density with Sharp Decline

Boroughs such as Camden, Haringey, and Tower Hamlets displayed consistently high outlet densities up to 15 minutes, followed by a sharp decline thereafter (Figure 6).

3.4 Low-Density with Extended Decline

Finally, boroughs including Bexley, Bromley, and Richmond presented a contrasting pattern, characterised by lower initial densities within the first 5 minutes, followed by a gradual increase, peaking between 5–10 minutes of walking time (Figure 7).

4. Discussion

The results highlight an overall high density of fast-food outlets within a 15-minute walk of schools in London, meaning that school children are more exposed to unhealthy food options in the immediate vicinity of their schools, than outside of it. A similar pattern was identified in Tower Hamlets by Caraher, Lloyd and Madelin (2014), and our study shows this trend is consistent across London. The distribution of fast-food outlets, however, varies across London boroughs. Central boroughs exhibit high densities of outlets near schools, while suburban boroughs show more dispersed patterns.

A key strength of this study lies in its methodology, which assesses outlet density relative to schools based on street networks and walking times rather than linear distances. This approach better reflects real-world accessibility and provides actionable insights for policymakers. While the study focuses on London, the methodology can be applied in other regions to analyse outlet distributions and design effective exclusion zones tailored to local contexts.

These findings have implications for public health and planning policy. The high density of fast-food outlets within a 30-minute round-trip walk highlights the need to implement policies, such as takeaway exclusion zones, to limit the proliferation of outlets in already saturated areas.

Our analysis suggests that restricting the establishment of new fast-food outlets within a 15-minute walk of London schools could effectively target areas of highest exposure for schoolchildren. However, variation in the distribution of outlets across boroughs indicates that a uniform, one-size-fits-all

approach to takeaway management zones may not adequately address the areas of greatest exposure for all schoolchildren.

To maximise the effectiveness of such policies, a focus on the immediate area outside of schools may not be sufficient. As indicated by our findings, boroughs with sustained high densities of fast-food outlets may require greater exclusion zones, and boroughs with additional outlet clusters beyond the immediate vicinity of schools, additional smaller exclusion zones at further distances, to cover high-exposure areas. However, in the absence of this, management zones that cover areas within a 15-minute walk of schools in London should be considered a reasonable minimum. By focusing on areas of greatest need, these measures could contribute to long-term public health improvements by reducing children’s access to unhealthy food environments.

5. Figures, Tables and Equations,

Figure 1 Raster surface of different travel time bands (minutes walk) from schools with fast-food outlets plotted for the borough of Croydon

Figure 2 Rho hat plot showing the density of fast-food outlets by minutes walk from schools for the borough of Croydon

Figure 3 Overlay of Rhoat Curves for all London Boroughs

Figure 4 Overlay of Rhoat Curves for density patterns with strong peaks and gradual declines

Figure 5 Overlay of Rhohat Curves for density patterns with strong peaks and noticeable secondary peaks

Figure 6 Overlay of Rhohat Curves for density patterns with sustained high density and sharp declines

Figure 7 Overlay of Rho-hat Curves for density patterns with low density and extended decline

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8. Biographies

Miss Chiara Gericke is a PhD student and Early Career Researcher (ECR) at University College London. Her research focuses on understanding the interplay between factors contributing to obesity, integrating methods from epidemiology, psychology, geography, and genetics. She is interested in the role of the built neighbourhood food environment and genetic factors in shaping eating behaviours and weight-related outcomes.

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Professor Adam Dennett is a Professor of Urban Analytics at UCL's Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis. His research focuses on population geography, migration modelling, census analysis, geodemographics, spatial statistics, and urban analytics.